

VIEWS ON MEMORY AND WAYS OF MEMORY DEVELOPMENT

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Annotatsiya: In this article, we will try to give brief information about how to improve human memory and how to develop it. In order to become a perfect person, a person needs spiritual and religious knowledge and experiences. In order to obtain such knowledge, which is necessary in human life, it is necessary for a person to have a perfect memory.

Key words: Memory, attention, voluntary and involuntary memory, thinking, emotions, mental activity, short-term and operational memories. Enter. The progress of a person, his development, his conquest of high peaks are directly related to his memory. As Sechenev said, a person without memory: "would have remained an infant forever" and S.I. Rubinstein's: "We would be minute creatures without memory" - these thoughts mean that without human memory, a baby born yesterday would not be it doesn't matter what.

Memory is the mental process of remembering and recalling perceived objects and events or past experiences. The following main processes are distinguished in the field of memory: remembering, remembering, recalling and forgetting. These processes do not occur in isolation. They form different aspects of one common process. Memory remembers the best moments. It is one of the properties of the nervous system, and it is manifested in the ability to store information about the events of the external world and reactions of the body for a long time, and to reproduce it in the activity of consciousness and in the framework of behavior and behavior. Memory is what an individual remembers, remembers, and later remembers in his experience.

The first scientific views on memory can be found in Eastern thinkers and Greek philosophers (Aristotle, Democritus, etc.). In particular, Farobi looks at memory as a component of the mental process of knowing, and emphasizes that memory is not only a characteristic of humans, but also of animals.

Memory is usually understood as remembering. But the preservation and later repetition of the conditions of life in the personal activity of a person is memory. Aristotle began to study this mental process in the 4th century BC. Through such

sciences as psychology, pedagogy, kibimetics, medicine, neurophysiology and biochemistry, we will be able to know that memory ensures the integrity of personal development. As stated by I.M. Sechenov, human life cannot be imagined without the process of memory. Any mental elements are retained by memory to "connect" each element to the next, even if there is a mistake.

The most important feature of all mental processes is memory. Memory ensures the integrity of the human personality. A person without memory is like a newborn baby.

The importance of memory occupies a great place in children of kindergarten age. They involuntarily remember things that are of some importance for their activities, that leave a strong impression on them and that interest them. They do not aim to remember something. They are still unable to set a goal. Memory, as one of the levels of reflection of the surrounding reality, is a set of general processes and consists of storing past experiences. The speech of teachers and parents plays an important role in developing children's memory. When talking to a child, the speech should be simple, the pronunciation of words should be clear and understandable. It plays a big role in the development of the child's memory and personal development.

E.S. As Rapasevich noted, "memory is a necessary condition for the unity of spiritual life, and man is the unity of his personality." Through memory, a person finds his skills and uses them at the right time, it is impossible to imagine any skill without consolidating it in the memory of a person.

In psychology, the following main types of memory are distinguished:

Memorize

Save

Forgetting

Reproduction (recognition recovery)

According to S.I. Rubinstein, associative, semantic and structural connections play an important role in the process of memorization "remembering is the application of currently acquired knowledge in practical or theoretical activities for the purpose of more or less conscious fixation." Remembering is like recalling practical knowledge for use in practical or theoretical activities and using it in the present tense. The role of the material is mainly manifested in these connections, but memorization depends not only on the objective connections of the material, but also on the person's relationship with it. Memorization is the process of fixing and storing in memory, the impressions obtained from the elements and events of reality. A memory can be:

Involuntarily, in such a case, the recollection of a predetermined goal in lasting memory and the continuation of our voluntary actions;

There is a specific goal to remember and some effort is made and this goal is achieved, characterized by the absence of a compelling goal to involuntarily memorize symbols.

Objects with distinct characteristics have been found to be easier and more involuntary to recall and proceed without much effort compared to forced memorization. Things related to a person's interests, certain feelings, and experiences have a significant impact on the duration of involuntary memorization. Volitional memorization is memorization characterized by consciously setting goals, making specific plans to remember specific material, and using other tricks. In order to achieve a goal, a person makes voluntary actions and has an effective memory.

Mechanical memorization: memorizing material without understanding the relationships between things. V.A. According to Krutetsky, children usually memorize in a mechanical way, children usually do not understand the educational material or do not want to understand it. A characteristic feature of logical memorization is that a person has a high interest in memorization, the opening of the semantics of the essence of the material of the memory consolidated in the memory is based on the understanding of the content of the logical connections between its parts. Permanent links are established between memorization and reproduction, which is called "retention" of things and events to be remembered.

E. S. Rapatsevich says that "retention is the preservation of memory, i.e. traces and connections in the brain." The retention of material in memory depends on its participation in the activity, because at any time the behavior of a person is determined by his entire experience. Forgetting-disappearance, the process of losing memory, and denial represent different features of the same process.

One of the first psychological theories of memory is the associative theory, which emerged in the 17th century and was the first to be developed in England and Germany in the 18th-19th centuries. This theory is based on association - the concept of connection between separate and unique phenomena of the psyche developed by G. Ebbinghaus, G. Müller, A. Pilsecker and others. According to this theory, memory is understood as a complex system of short-term and long-term associations that are stable in terms of similarity, temporal and

spatial resolution. According to this theory, many laws were discovered, in particular, the law of forgetting by G. Ebbinghaus. Up to 60% of the information received during the first hour is forgotten, and after six days, less than 20% of the text memorized for the first time is retained. Over time, the associative theory faces a number of problems that need to be solved. The main one was to explain the selective nature of human memory. As the initial concept for this theory, and at the same time as the main principle that can explain the unique phenomena of memory, not the association of the primary elements, but their initial integrated organization - Helstein appeared.

In modern psychology, the theory that studies the formation of all mental processes of a person, as well as the formation of memory processes, is recognized as the main concept. Based on this concept, the process of memorizing, storing and recalling is determined by the position of information as an object.

In world psychology, this concept was developed in the cultural-historical theory of the origin of human higher mental tasks produced by L.S. Vygotsky. A.N. Leontev, A.R. Luria, A.A. It was developed by Smirov and other famous psychologists.

As a result of brain plasticity and quiet decline, it causes memory loss and sometimes fatigue. As a result of a person's rest, he is restored. But as age passes, it weakens. For example, elderly people forget what they are saying or repeat what they have said before. Temporary neural connections are a physiological mechanism that creates associations.

Depending on the nature of mental activity, which is more visible in the activity, it is divided into action, emotional, verbal, logical and figurative memories;

According to the goals of the activity: voluntary and involuntary memories are included;

According to how long the material can be remembered and remembered: it is divided into short-term, long-term and operational memories;

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